

SYNTHESIS AND BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF 2H(SUBSTITUTED)-1,3-BENZOTHAZOLE COMPOUNDS IN A MICROWAVE REACTOR

M.I. Olimova¹, E.R. Kurbanova², I.E. Yuldashova³, B.Zh. Elmuradov⁴

S. Yunusov Institute of the Chemistry of Plant Substances, Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan^{1,2,3,4}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16745411>

Abstract. In our research, the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles in high yields was carried out using a catalyst-free microwave reactor within a short period of time. For this purpose, *o*-aminothiophenol:aldehydes were mixed in a 1:1 ratio in the solvent of ethanol:water with 1:1 ratio. The chemical reaction was carried out in a microwave reactor at 65W for 5 minutes. During the reaction, it was observed that the yield of the reaction product increased with increasing time. As a result, products with average and good yields were synthesized initially in 3-4 minutes, and with good and high yields in 5 minutes. The inhibitory and growth-promoting activities of the synthesized compounds were tested against the growth of cucumber seeds of the Orzu variety in 0.1%, 0.01% and 0.001% solutions of the compounds.

Keywords: *o*-aminothiophenol, 4-methoxybenzoic aldehyde, *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, *p*-methylbenzaldehyde, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, 3,4-dimethoxybenzoic aldehyde, 3,4,5 trimethoxybenzoic aldehyde, 2-(3,4 dimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole, 2-(4-chlorophenyl) benzothiazole, 2-(4-dimethylamino) benzothiazole i 2-(2-chlorophenyl) benzothiazole, 2-(3,4,5 trimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole, inhibitor and grower.

Introduction: 2H(Substituted)-benzothiazoles are widespread compounds, which are distinguished by the presence of various biologically active substances. Therefore, great attention is paid to the methods of synthesis of this class of compounds [1; pp. 174-185].

The preparation of 2-substituted (or 2-unsubstituted) benzothiazoles by the reactions of *o*-aminothiophenols with aldehydes [2; pp. 11185-11192], acids [3; pp. 2440-2443], acid chlorides [4; pp. 175-178], nitriles [5; pp. 1598-1601], or esters [6; pp. 313-316], as well as by the cyclization of thiobenzanilides, has been widely described in the literature [7; pp. 439-445, 8; pp. 2026-2029, 9; pp. 3687-3689, 10; pp. 1802-1807].

The authors Liu and Chung [11; pp. 56958-56960, 12; pp. 6648-6652, 13; pp. 3438-3442] proposed a method (i) for the preparation of benzothiazoles from 2-aminothiophenol in the presence of a catalyst, silane, and CO₂:

i: Catalyst, source, CO₂ (atm), NMP, 60°C, 18 h;

ii: DBN, Et₂SiH₂, CO₂ (5MPa), 150°C;

iii: (Bmim)(OAc), (EtO)₃SiH, CO₂ (0.5MPa).

However, these methods require special reactors to carry out the reactions and require the use of a limited number of substrates, which limits the wide application of these methods (i-iii) in

practice. Therefore, the authors [1;174-185p.] developed a cyclization reaction of 2-aminothiophenols (I) with a dimethylformamide derivative (carbon source) and imidazole chloride. This method has a number of advantages due to the use of inexpensive and stable starting materials:

The use of this method allowed the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles with a yield of 60-87%. The authors [14; pp. 3821-3828] developed a one-step method for the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles:

The advantage of this method is that the corresponding benzothiazoles (IV) were synthesized in 61-81% yields by oxidation-cyclization reaction from substituted o-aminothiophenols (I) and benzylamines in the presence of oxidants (iodine) at room temperature.

In research papers, it can be found that some medication were created from benzothiazoles against cancer [15; pp. 5424-5427, 16; 7095-7103 p.], microbes [17; 1795-1801 p., 18; pp. 3681-3685, 19; 5599-5608 p.], inflammation [20; p. 34-38], tuberculosis [21; pp. 137-145, 22; p. 275-281], AIDS (Acquired immune deficiency syndrome) [23; 868-882 p.] and malaria [24; 995-998 p.], some medicine with anti-convulsant [25; 1345-1349 p.], anthelmintic [26; pp. 459-464, 27; p. 439-442], antioxidant [28; 2228-2232 p.] and bactericidal [29; 118-125 p.]

Benzothiazoles with high synthetic potential are still an interesting object among chemists and biologists. Benzothiazoles are used by scientists as important heterocycles for modern organic synthesis and pharmaceutical chemistry. The chemical structures of several clinically important drugs containing the benzothiazole ring are presented below, including Riluzole, Ethoxazolamide, Dimazole, Pittsburgh Compound V, and Flutemetamol:

Continuing our research, we have carried out the synthesis of 2-substituted benzothiazoles in a short time and with good and high yields using a catalyst-free microwave reactor, a method not yet found in the literature. In this case, o-aminothiophenol: aldehydes were mixed in a 1:1 ratio in the solvent of ethanol: water in 1:1 ratio, and the reaction was carried out in a chemical

microwave reactor at 65W for 5 minutes. During the reaction, an increase in the yield of the reaction product was observed with increasing time. It should be noted that the reactions were carried out in two (A and B) methods. According to method A, a 1:1 mixture of *o*-aminothiophenol (I) and aldehyde was mixed in a 1:1 ethanol: water solvent, stirred and heated at room temperature for 4 hours, and high yields of 2-substituted 1,3-benzothiazoles were synthesized. In method B, a 1:1 mixture of *o*-aminothiophenol (I) and aldehyde was mixed in a 1:1 ethanol: water solvent, and the products were synthesized in a chemical microwave reactor at 65W in 3-4 minutes with average and good yields, and in 5 minutes with good and high yields (Table 1).

A) *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde, B) *p*-methylbenzaldehyde, C) *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, D) *p*-nitrobenzaldehyde, E) 4-methoxybenzoic aldehyde, F) 3,4-dimethoxybenzoic aldehyde, G) 3,4,5 trimethoxybenzoic aldehyde, H) 2-chlorobenzaldehyde

Table - 1

№	Gross fomula	Rf	Liquidation temperature, °C	Reaction yield (%) 4 hours	Reaction yield (%) MW, 5 min
2	C ₁₃ H ₈ SNCl	0.77	114-116	99	96
3	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ SN	0.75	77-78	97	95
4	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ SN ₂	0.6	169-171	96	94
5	C ₁₃ H ₈ SN ₂ O ₂	0.47	218-220	88	86
6	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ SNO	0.64	119-120	95	91
7	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ SNO ₂	0.38	130-132	94	90
8	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ SNO ₃	0.5	149-150	85	78
9	C ₁₃ H ₈ SNCl	0.8	76-77	80	79

Biology. Benzothiazolin-2-thione, its derivatives and heterocyclic analogues also exhibit various biological activities. Among them, fungicides, herbicides and plant growth regulators have been found. Hence, in order to continue research by searching for new biologically active substances, scientific studies have been carried out to study the inhibitory and growth-promoting activities of this class of compounds. Conducting these studies is interesting not only from a theoretical but also from a practical point of view.

Experimental procedure

To determine the inhibitory and growth-stimulating activity, cucumber seeds of the Orzu variety were soaked in test solutions at 0.1%, 0.01% and 0.001% concentrations; in the control,

the seeds were soaked in ordinary water. The biological activity was assessed based on the linear growth rates of the root and stem parts of the plants on the 5th day [33]. Statistical data processing was performed using the Origin Pro program [34].

Table 2. Effect of synthetic substances on the biological activity of seeds

Experimental options	Concentration, %	Germination, %	Root length, Sm	Shoot length, sm
Control	6/o	97,2±2,04	5,88±1,14	5,16±0,58
2-(4-chloro-phenyl) benzothiazole	0,1	53,5±2,39	1,24±0,48	0±0
	0,01	67,8±1,44	2,92±0,62	1,32±0,51
	0,001	89,2±2,39	4,86±0,69	2,84±0,59
2-(3,4 dimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole	0,1	47,3±1,25	0,62±0,42	0±0
	0,01	62,5±1,44	2,98±0,78	1,48±0,41
	0,001	86,5±2,04	3,52±1,3	2,14±0,45
2-(3,4,5 trimethoxy-phenyl) benzothiazole	0,1	82,9±1,25	5,86±0,76	3,8±0,39
	0,01	90,3±1,25	5,76±0,63	4,46±0,37
	0,001	96,7±2,07	6,92±0,61	6,1±0,5
2-(4-dimetil-amino) benzothiazole	0,1	41,8±1,35	1,78±1,22	0,85±0,34
	0,01	74,5±2,33	3,38±1,18	2,14±0,4
	0,001	88,9±1,25	5,16±0,53	5,2±0,98
2-(2-chloro-phenyl) benzothiazole	0,1	44,5±1,44	1,66±0,59	0,28±0,91
	0,01	62,5±1,38	3,88±0,67	2,28±0,67
	0,001	77,6±1,41	4,4±1,32	3,12±0,56

As our studies have shown, in all experimental variants in 0.1% concentration, except for the 2-(3,4,5 trimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole variant, a decrease in cucumber seed germination to 41.8% - 53.5% is observed, while in the control, germination reached 97.2%. In the 2-(3,4,5 trimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole variant in 0.1% concentration, germination reached 82.9%. It can also be noted that with a decrease in concentration in this variant to 0.001%, growth-stimulating activity was observed. The length of the roots exceeded the control variant by 17.6%, the length of the shoot by 18.2%. Screening for inhibitory activity revealed the most active substance to be 2-(3,4 dimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole at 0.1% concentration, in which the inhibition of the root part was 89.5%, and of the stem part 100% relative to the control variant. This activity was also retained at 0.01%, in which the suppression of cucumber seedlings was 41.4% and 71.4%.

In the following experimental variants 2-(4-chlorophenyl) benzothiazole, 2-(4-dimetilamino) benzothiazole and 2-(2-chlorophenyl) benzothiazole, in high concentration the suppression of the root part of cucumber relative to the control variant was 100%, 69.8% and 71.8%, shoots 74.5%, 83.6% and 94.5%, respectively. With a decrease in concentration to 0.01% the activity decreased. Thus, the inhibition of the roots was 50.4%, 42.6% and 34.1%, the stem part 74.5%, 58.6% and 55.9 relative to the control.

Consequently, it was established that the synthetic substances 2-(3,4 dimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole, 2-(4-chlorophenyl) benzothiazole, 2-(4-dimetilamino) benzothiazole and 2-(2-

chlorophenyl) benzothiazole at high concentrations have an inhibitory property. The experiment conducted, according to the initial assessment of biological activity, revealed that the variant 2-(3,4,5 trimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole at 0.001% concentration exhibits growth-stimulating activity.

Experiment part

2-(4-chlorophenyl)benzothiazole.

3.88 g (31.04 mmol) of o-aminothiophenol was dissolved in 50 ml of ethanol : water 1:1 solvent, for which 4.36 g of p-chlorobenzaldehyde was added. The reaction mixture was heated in a microwave reactor for 5 minutes. After the reaction was complete (checked using UV light) and the mixture was cooled, the precipitate was filtered. It was washed with petroleum ether and dried. After recrystallization of the technical substance from ethanol, white-yellow crystals were obtained. Yield 7.31 g (96%), melting point 114-116⁰C, ¹H NMR(400MHz DMSO-d₆) δ 8.15(d, J 7.3Hz, 1H, ArH), 8.05(d, J 8.4 Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.80 (d, J 7.3 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.41(t, J 7.6 Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.30(t, J 7.6 Hz, 1H, ArH),7.16(d, J 8.22Hz, 2H, ArH); m/z 246(M+H). C₁₃H₈ClNS. R_f=0.77. System: Hexane:ethyl acetate 5:1.

2-(4-methylphenyl) benzothiazole.

The reaction was carried out similarly to the abovementioned method. 4.425 g (35.4 mmol) of o-aminothiophenol was dissolved in 50 ml of ethanol: water 1:1 solvent, and 4.248 g (35.4 mmol) p-methylbenzaldehyde was added. After the completed reaction, the precipitate was filtered. It was washed with petroleum ether and dried. The technical substance was recrystallized from ethanol to obtain a yellow compound. Yield 7.73 g (97%), mp 77-78⁰C, ¹H NMR (400MHz DMSO-d₆) δ 7.92-8.10(m 3H Ar H), 7.41(t J 7.38Hz, 1H Ar H), 7.30 (t J 7.38Hz, 1H Ar H), 7.26(d J 8.12Hz 2H Ar H),2.45(s 3H CH₃); m/z 226(M+H). R_f=0.75. System: Hexane:ethyl acetate 5:1.

2-(4-Nitrophenyl) benzothiazole.

By implementing similar methodology as it was mentioned above, 0.472 g (3.8 mmol) of o-aminothiophenol was dissolved in 15 ml of ethanol: water 1:1 solvent, and 0.570 g (3.8 mmol) p-nitrobenzaldehyde was added. Once the reaction had concluded, the mixture was cooled, and the precipitate was filtered. It was washed with petroleum ether and dried. The technical substance was recrystallized from ethanol to obtain an orange-colored substance. Yield 0.84 g (86%), melting point 218-220⁰C, ¹H NMR(400MHz DMSO-d₆) δ 8.9 (d, J 8.0 Hz, 2H, Ar-H); 8.32 (d, J 8.0 Hz, 2H, Ar- H); 8.23 (d, J 8.0 Hz, 1H, Ar-H); 8.02 (d, J 8.0 Hz, 1H, Ar- H); 7.44-7.53 (m, 2H, Ar-H); m/z 256 (M+H). C₁₃H₈N₂O₂S. R_f=0.47. System: Hexane:ethyl acetate 5:1.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)benzothiazole.

Based on same methodology, 3 g (24 mmol) of o-aminothiophenol was dissolved in 50 ml of ethanol: water 1:1 solvent, for which 3.264 g (24 mmol) of p-methoxybenzaldehyde was added. After the reaction completion, the precipitate was filtered. It was washed with petroleum ether and dried. The technical substance was recrystallized from ethanol to give a light-yellow substance. Yield 5.2 g (90%), melting point 119-120⁰C, ¹H NMR (400MHz DMSO) δ 8.19(d, J 8.22Hz, 1H,ArH), 8.05(d, J 8.22Hz, 1H, ArH), 7.07(d, J 7.75Hz, 2H, ArH), 7.12-7.41(m, 4H, ArH), 3.92(s 3H, OCH₃); m/z 242(M+H). C₁₄H₁₁NOS, R_f=0.64. System: Hexane:ethyl acetate 5:1.

2-(3,4,5 trimethoxyphenyl) benzothiazole.

In similar manner, 1.187 g (9.5 mmol) of o-aminothiophenol was dissolved in 25 ml of ethanol: water 1:1 solvent, which in turn was combined with 1.86 g (9.5 mmol) of 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde. At the end of the reaction, the precipitate was filtered. It was washed with petroleum ether and dried. After recrystallization of the technical substance from ethanol, a

white-yellow crystalline substance was obtained. Yield 2.23 g (78%), melting point 149-150°C, ¹H NMR(400MHz DMSO-d₆) δ 8.31(t, 1H, ArH), 8.22(t, 1H, ArH), 7.45(dd J 2.42Hz,7.55Hz, 2H, ArH), 6.57(d, J 2.42Hz, 2H, ArH), 3.61(s, 9H, OCH₃).;m/z 302(M+H). C₁₆H₁₅NO₃S. R_f=0.5. System: Hexane:ethyl acetate 5:1.

Conclusion and Acknowledgements: The authors were awarded a scholarship from the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the project “Creation of scientific foundations for targeted synthesis of new, highly biologically active synthetic and natural compounds for the needs of agriculture and medicine using modern methods of organic synthesis.” expresses its gratitude for the financial support provided within the framework of the research program.

REFERENCES

1. Tian Q., Luo W., Gan Z., Li D., Dai Z., Wang H., Wang X., Yuan J. Eco-Friendly Syntheses of 2-Substituted Benzoxazoles and 2-Substituted Benzothiazoles from 2-Aminophenols, 2-Aminothiophenols and DMF Derivatives in the Presence of Imidazolium Chloride // *Molecules*. -2019. -№24. -P.174-186.
2. Suvendu S., Sudipto D., Papu B. Photocatalysis by 3,6-Disubstituted-s-Tetra-zine: Visible-Light Driven Metal-Free Green Synthesis of 2-Substituted Benz-imidazole and Benzothiazole // *J. Org. Chem.* -2014. -№45. -P.11184-11193.
3. Wen X., Bakali J.E., Deprez-Poulain R., Deprez B. Efficient propyl-phosphonic anhydride (®T3P) mediated synthesis of benzothiazoles, benzoxazoles and benzimidazoles // *Tetrahedron Lett.* -2012. -№53. -P.2440-2443.
4. Pottorf R.S., Chadha N.K., Katkevics M., Ozola V., Suna E., Ghane H., Regberg T., Player M.R. Parallel synthesis of benzoxazoles via microwave-assisted dielectric heating // *Tetrahedron Lett.* -2003. -№44. -P.175-178.
5. Yadong S., Huanfeng J., Wanqing W., Wei Z., Xia W. Copper-catalyzed synthesis of substituted benzothiazoles via condensation of 2-amino-benzenethiols with nitriles // *Org. Lett.* -2013. -№15. -P.1598-1601.
6. Matsushita H., Lee S.-H., Joung M., Clapham B., Janda K.D. Smart cleavage reactions: The synthesis of benzimidazoles and benzothiazoles from polymer-bound esters // *Tetrahedron Lett.* -2004. -№45. -P.313-316.
7. Sahoo S.K., Khatun N., Gogoi A., Deb A., Patel B.K. Cu(ii) catalysed chemoselective oxidative transformation of thiourea to thioamidoguanidine /2-aminobenzothiazole // *RSC Adv.* -2013. -№3. -P.438-446.
8. Liu K., Jia F., Xi H., Li Y., Zheng X., Guo Q., Shen B., Li Z. Direct benzo-thiophene formation via oxygen-triggered intermolecular cyclization of thiophenols and alkynes assisted by manganese/PhCOOH // *Org. Lett.* -2013. -№15. -P.2026-2029.
9. Itoh T., Mase T. A novel practical synthesis of benzothiazoles via Pd-catalyzed thiol cross-coupling // *Org. Lett.* -2007. -Vol.9. -№18. -P.3687-3689.
10. Evindar G., Batey R.A. Parallel synthesis of a library of benzoxazoles and benzothiazoles using ligand-accelerated copper-catalyzed cyclizations of ortho-halobenzanilides // *J. Org. Chem.* -2006. -№71. -P.1802-1808.
11. Gao X., Yu B., Zhao Y., Hao L., Liu Z. Hydrosilane-promoted cyclization of 2-aminothiophenols by CO₂ to benzothiazoles // *RSC Adv.* -2014. -№4. -P.56957-56960.

12. Gao X., Yu B., Yang Z., Zhao Y., Zhang H., Hao L., Han B., Liu Z. Ionic Liquid-Catalyzed C–S Bond Construction using CO₂ as a C1 Building Block under Mild Conditions: A Metal-Free Route to Synthesis of Benzothiazoles // *ACS Catal.* -2015. -№5. -P.6648–6652.
13. Chun S., Yang S., Chung Y.K. Synthesis of benzothiazoles from 2-amino-benzenethiols in the presence of a reusable polythiazolium precatalyst under atmospheric pressure of carbon dioxide // *Tetrahedron.* -2017. -№73. -P.3438–3442.
14. Naresh G., Kant R., Narender T. Molecular Iodine Promoted Divergent Synthesis of Benzimidazoles, Benzothiazoles and 2-Benzyl-3-phenyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-benzo[e][1,2,4]thiadiazines // *J.Org.Chem.* -2014. -№79. -P.3821-3829.
15. Kumbhare R.M., Kosurkar U.B., Ramaiah M.J., Dadmal T.L., Pushpavalli S.N., Bhadra M.P. Synthesis and biological evaluation of novel triazoles and isoxazoles linked 2-phenyl benzothiazole as potential anticancer agents // *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* -2012. -Vol.22. - Issue 17. -P.5424-5427.
16. Hiyoshi H., Goto N., Tsuchiya M., Iida K., Nakajima Y., Hirata N., Kanda Y., Nagasawa K., Yanagisawa J. 2-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-benzothiazole suppresses tumor progression and metastatic potential of breast cancer cells by inducing ubiquitin ligase CHIP // *Sci. Rep.* -2014. -№4. -P.7095-7104.
17. Prajapat P., Rathore K.K., Gandhi D., Agarwal S., Hussain N., Yogi P., Talesara G.L. A facile synthesis of biologically significant 2-(1,3-benzothiazol-2-ylimino)-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one / 3-(1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-2-thioxoimidazolidin-4-on analogues from 1-(1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl) thiourea and their alphahydroxylamine derivatives // *Iranian J. Org. Chem.* -2016. -Vol.8. -Issue 2. -P.1795-1801.
18. Cano N.H., Ballari M.S., Lopez A.G., Santiago A.N. New synthesis and biological evaluation of benzothiazole derivates as antifungal agents // *J. Agri. Food Chem.* -2015. -Vol.63. -Issue 14. -P.3681-3686.
19. Patel R.V., Park S.W. Catalytic N-formylation for synthesis of 6-substituted-2-benzothiazolylimino-5-piperazinyl-4-thiazolidinone antimicrobial agents // *Res. Chem. Intermed.* -2015. -Vol.41. -Issue 8. -P. 5599-5609.
20. Mahtab R., Srivastava A., Gupta N., Kushwaha S.K., Tripathi A. Synthesis of novel 2-benzylbenzo[d] thiazole-6-sulfonamide derivatives as potential antiinflammatory agent // *J. Chem. Pharma. Sci.* -2014. -№7. -P.34-38.
21. Hazra K., Nargund L.V.G., Rashmi P., Chandra J.N.N.S., Nandha B., Harish M.S. Synthesis and comparative study of anti-mycobacterium activity of a novel series of fluoronitrobenzothiazolopyrazoline regioisomers // *Arch. Pharm. Chem. Life Sci.* -2012. - Vol.345. -Issue 2. -P.137-146.
22. Mir F., Shafi S., Zaman M.S., Kalia N.P., Rajput V.S., Mulakayala C., Mulakayala N., Khan I.A., Alam M.S. Sulfur rich 2-mercaptobenzothiazole and 1,2,3-triazole conjugates as novel antitubercular agents // *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* -2014. -№76. -P.274-283.
23. Xu Y.S., Zeng C.C., Jiao Z.G., Hu L.M., Zhong R.G. Design, synthesis and anti-HIV integrase evaluation of 4-oxo-4H-quinolizine-3-carboxylic acid derivatives // *Molecules.* -2009. - Vol.14. -Issue 2. -P.868-883.
24. Takasu K., Inoue H., Kim H., Suzuki M., Shishido T., Wataya Y., Ihara M. Rhodacyanine dyes as antimalarials. Preliminary evaluation of their activity and toxicity // *J. Med. Chem.* - 2002. -Vol.45. -Issue 5. -P.995-998.

25. Siddiqui N., Rana A., Khan S.A., Haque S.E., Alam M.S., Haque S.E., Alam M.S., Ahsan W., Ahmed S. Synthesis of 8-substituted-4-(2/4-substituted phenyl)-2H-[1,3,5]triazino[2,1-b][1,3]benzothiazole-2-thiones and their anticonvulsant, anti-nociceptive, and toxicity evaluation in mice // J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem. -2009. -Vol.24. -Issue 6. -P.1344-1350.
26. Munirajasekhar D., Himaja M., Malib S.V. A facile and efficient synthesis of 2-(5-(4-Substitutedphenyl)-4,5-dihydro-3-phenylpyrazol-1-yl)-6-substituted benzothiazoles and their biological studies // J. Heterocyclic. Chem. -2014. -Vol.51. -Issue 2. -P.459-465.
27. Sarkar S., Dwivedi J., Chauhan R. Synthesis of 1-[2 (substituted phenyl)-4-oxothiazolidin-3-yl]-3-(6-fluro-7-chloro-1,3-benzothiazol-2-yl)-ureas as anthelmintic agent // J. Pharm. Res. -2013. -Vol.7. -Issue 5. -P.439-442.
28. Gouda M.A., Eldien H.F., Girges M.M., Berghot M.A. Synthesis and antioxidant activity of novel series of naphthoquinone derivatives attached to benzothiophene moiety // Med. Chem. -2013. -Vol.3. -Issue 2. -P.2228-2232.
29. Kumawat M., Kherodiya B., Prajapat P., Talesara G.L. Synthesis of alkoxyphthalimide derivatized oxoimidazolidinyl oxazolo/thiazolo dihydropyrimidine and oxoimidazolidinyl tetrahydropyrimidine via common Schiff base intermediate and evaluation of their antibacterial activity // Indian J. Chem. -2015. -Vol.54B. -Issue 1. -P.117-127.
30. Olimova M.I., Zakirova R.P., Elmurodov B.Zh. Herbicidal, drowth-promoting and fungicidal activities of some cyanoethyl and amidomethyl derivatives of benzimidazoles, benzothiazoles and benzopyrimidine. UNIVERSUM Journal: Chemistry and Biology. June, 2020, No 6 (72) pp. 19-22
31. Origin Program V8.6 and Statistics. Scientific graphing and analysis software.